

The relationship between digital data privacy and the usage of social media applications

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ABSTRACT

Recent privacy-related issues regarding social media applications among students have demonstrated that the phenomenon ‘privacy paradox’ is the situation where people’s intentions to safeguard their privacy conflicts with how they operate in the online environment is not consistent, which might influence users’ intention to use a social media app. In this study, two variables - length of a privacy statement and app permission requests - have been researched that might have influence on the intention to use a social media app. These variables were examined to conclude the users’ intention to use a social media app. An online survey has been conducted with 106 participants. Results show that the length of the privacy statement does not have any effect on the user’s intention to use an app. The survey results show that the amount of app permission requests does not have a significant influence on the user’s intent to use a social media app.

Keywords: Digital privacy; privacy statements; social media apps; permission sensitivity; mobile users

INTRODUCTION

The mobile application (app) ecosystem, which includes billions of smartphone users and millions of app developers, has evolved to become one of the largest industries in the world. Since 2021 more than 230 billion mobile applications have been downloaded with gaming, social networking, entertainment, news and apps for health, fitness and lifestyle being the most popular app categories (Reychav et al., 2019; Statista, 2022). As the availability and downloads of mobile apps increase rapidly, the risks for the mobile users’ privacy and security increases as well.

Since social media app usage continues to grow, privacy concerns are becoming more and more prevalent. The privacy concerns of digital

data across social media apps have drawn a lot of attention in information systems (IS) research. Previous studies have shown that privacy has become a priority for mobile users across digital channels (Degirmenci, 2020; Rath & Kumar, 2021). Digital data privacy is an important focus area in today’s day and age, where information could be captured, shared, and stored with a click of a button (Pelteret & Ophoff, 2016).

As mobile applications may present multiple privacy concerns due to a large amount of personal information that may be gathered, utilised and shared by the millions of applications on the market. Permission requests from apps enable users to maintain control over their data. In addition to personal information, apps will need permission to access different features of the mobile device (Bracamonte et al., 2022; Reputation Science, 2018).

However, it is interesting to note that even though people have growing privacy concerns, social media users continue to divulge their personal information on social media platforms. Rather than protecting and reducing their social media usage. Numerous studies have documented this as the phenomenon of privacy paradox, which refers to the disparity between people’s intentions to disclose personal information and their actual personal information behaviours, which are frequently not the same (Alemany et al., 2021; Bright et al., 2021; Chen, 2018; Debatin et al., 2009).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Students are using social media more frequently, according to authors like Mulisa and Getahun (2018) the younger generation is the largest user of social media. Moallem claims that since social media is the primary means of communication for today’s college students, the students are much more at risk of reputational damage or financial loss than previous generations (2019). Furthermore, according to Sharma, Jain and

Tiwari (2015), 85% of students believe that sharing personal information on social media apps is risky. To amplify, several previous studies have found that high school students and adolescents are aware of the risks of using social media apps, and can even provide examples of problems that can occur. These studies have discovered that when adolescents were asked, they placed high importance on privacy and data protection, however the findings regarding their actual behaviour are contrary. On one hand, adolescents support the findings described above, demonstrating that students are aware of privacy concerns and potential threats. On the other hand, their behaviour in other contexts does not reflect the high value they have put on privacy and data protection. In addition, it was also clear that the most common reason for not using security settings was that they are difficult to understand and to use (Bhatnagar & Pry, 2020; Gogus & Saygin, 2019; Soffer & Cohen, 2014)

The researchers identified an apparent knowledge gap regarding the effectiveness of privacy statements in social media apps and the relationship between privacy statements and the intention to use an app among university students. Since students of the age group ranging from 20 - 29 are the largest social media app users of all other age groups. By far, a series of studies (Alemany et al., 2021; Bright et al., 2021; Chen, 2018; Debatin et al., 2009) have shown that the phenomenon 'privacy paradox' is the situation where people's intentions to safeguard their privacy conflicts with how they operate in the online environment is not consistent. However, recent studies have revealed that app stores and providers are confronted with the complexity of mobile users' information privacy issues, which could discourage users from installing mobile applications or lead them to uninstall an app (Degirmenci 2020). In addition, from the previous studies it was not evident whether personal data and privacy statements of mobile apps lose their effect the more app permissions are perceived to be of concern.

To emphasise, no research has been found that surveyed university students' social media app usage in relation to privacy statements. This encompasses several unexplored dimensions that lately have attracted research attention in other disciplines (Degirmenci, 2020; Harris et al., 2016). The research on privacy concerns regarding social media apps' privacy statements among Dutch universities should be explored further to provide an understanding as to why such is not the case with the privacy paradox as well as the intention to use an app.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The knowledge gap stated in the problem statement led to the following central research question:

To what extent do privacy statements of social media apps affect the users' intention to use the app?

To answer this research question, the following theoretical and practical sub questions were formulated.

Sub Questions:

1. How to determine a social media app's popularity?
2. What factors influence the intention to use mobile apps regarding privacy?
3. How do privacy statements influence the intention to use an app?

THEORY

A network effect occurs when the number of persons or participants increases the value of an item or service. A network effect may improve the experience as more individuals participate, but it may also promote new participants as they seek to benefit from the network. While network effects and network externalities are similar, network externalities show how the demand for one product is influenced by the demand of those who will also purchase it. In other words, the purchase habits of customers are influenced by what others buy. A network effect may result from positive network externalities. When a substantial number of individuals are using a specific app, people are more likely to download and use that app. If a person posts content of quality it will lead to more people enjoying that app, thus leading to an engagement boost, which will create a network effect (Banton, 2022; Stobierski, 2020).

Up to now, several studies have revealed that privacy concerns of mobile users have a significant impact on using mobile apps. For instance, the following research of Degirmenci (2020) has examined that mobile users' concerns for app permission requests have a significant impact on mobile users' overall information privacy concern. It became evident that excessive and irrelevant app permission requests have a negative impact on users' privacy concerns and might discourage users from downloading mobile apps or make them even uncomfortable, which can lead to users to uninstall an app. In fact, another study of Harris et al. (2016) discovered that digital security concerns have a major influence on mobile users' intention to install and use mobile apps. Starbucks, for example,

admitted in 2015 that hackers have hacked into the Starbucks mobile app to access customer information, which led to a large number of mobile users to delete the app out of fear (Gross, 2015; Pagliery, 2015). Additionally, the findings of Gu et al. (2017) provided practical implications for app developers, app stores and mobile users, as it is crucial for developers and app stores to comprehend customers' privacy concerns at this level because their financial success depends on app instalments. Because perceived permission sensitivity significantly raises privacy concerns and subsequently discourages download intention of mobile users.

Prior research has demonstrated that user attitudes and decisions to use mobile apps or disclosing personal information can be influenced directly and indirectly by privacy. According to the research of Wotrich, van Reijmersdal, and Smit (2018), discovered that mobile app users' perceptions of privacy concerns in Western Europe had a negative impact on whether they would provide permission for the app to access their personal information. It has been shown in numerous studies that user's willingness to divulge personal information (such as identification, location, and photos) to mobile apps (Xu et al., 2009) and intention to adopt mobile apps (Luo, Li, Zhang, & Shim, 2010).

Figure 1. Conceptual model

The conceptual model shown in figure 1 will discuss the interest to use an app as the independent variable. Within several probabilities that can lead to the intention to use an app, this study focuses on the amount of permission, length of privacy statement. In addition, the interest in an app is affected by network externalities.

To work optimally, an application needs to request permissions to use other features of the mobile device, to collect data, or other reasons. This permission should be explained clearly in the privacy statement to provide clear information to the user, however "From a practical perspective, app stores and providers should be alarmed that unnecessary and excessive app permission requests have a strong effect on users' privacy concerns, which can prevent users from installing mobile apps or make them feel uncomfortable with the result being that they uninstall an app"(Degirmenci,

2020). The overall information privacy concerns of mobile consumers are significantly impacted by app permission concerns (Degirmenci, 2020).

With the extensive list of permission this can lead to the privacy statement of an application to be lengthy. However, a thorough (lengthy) privacy statement enhances transparency by offering a single location where an interested reader may obtain the "whole story" of an organisation's privacy practices. In addition, it also promotes organisational accountability as it requires organisations to have a meticulous investigation of how the data is collected and processed in their practice. Although, little read through the whole privacy statement. (Hintze, 2017).

The following hypotheses are therefore put forward:

H1: The length of privacy statement has positive impact on the user's intention to use an app

H2: The amount of app permission requests has a positive impact on the user's intention to use an app.

METHODOLOGY

To provide definitive answers to the subquestions, a literature review has been performed, to look for the different variables. As two variables have been found that might influence the intention to use a social media app. To guarantee the reliability of the research only academic literature - which has been peer-reviewed - will be considered, in order to write the theory of the paper.

The target population has been defined as "Dutch university students". Which has been categorised as a heterogeneous population. According to the most recent statistics the number of Dutch university students in 2021-2022 consisted of 836,220, which has been used as a base (CBS Statline, 2022).

Sample size

A non-probability sampling technique, specifically convenience sampling, was used in determining the necessary sample size (Vehovar et al., 2016) The sample size was determined by the following formula (Smith, 2015) :

$$\text{Necessary Sample Size} = \frac{(z \text{ score})^2 * \text{StdDev} * (1 - \text{StdDev})}{(\text{margin of error})^2}$$

The following variables are used to calculate the sample size. The population size of 836,220, the confidence interval is 95%, a margin of error is 5% and a standard deviation of .5. This results in

a necessary sample size of 384.

Measurement procedure and instruments

The survey consisted of general questions (Table 1) and questions used for measuring the intention to use a social media app (Table 2). Qualtrics has been chosen as the survey platform to ask the questions to the respondents. Prior to taking part in the survey, respondents agreed to treat their answers with strict confidentiality, where anonymity was also a guarantee. These responses were collected over a 9-day period.

To increase the validity of this study, several steps were taken. All participants were given the same handling for the survey research, they received a textual instruction about the study which was included in the survey. Furthermore, all questions are multi-item measurement scales (5 point Likert Scale) to increase validity through higher construct and criterion validity (Sarstedt & Wilczynski, 2009)

Measurement Reliability

The reliability was measured using Cronbach's alpha which should be between 0 and 1, where a Cronbach's alpha of at least .7 is

considered a decent level of reliability (Bougie & Sekaran, 2016). Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the reliability of the survey measures, using an alpha of .05. The specific results and values are explained in the results of this study.

Table 1. General questions regarding the respondents and their app usage

Category	Questions	Type
General questions	GQ1: What's your gender?	Single answer - Male - Female - Non-binary/ third gender - Prefer not to say
	GQ2: What's your age?	Open number between 0 - 99
	GQ3: Are you a student at a University (or University of Applied Sciences) in The Netherlands	Single answer - Yes - No
	GQ4: What do you study?	Single answer - HBO Bachelor (Applied university) - WO Bachelor (University) - HBO Master - Premaster - WO Master - Postmaster - PhD
	GQ5: What field are you studying?	Single answer - Arts - Science and Math - Environment - Business - Engineering - Literature, Language and Social Science - Medicine - Other: ...
General app questions	GAQ1: What social media apps do you use?	Multiple choice - Whatsapp - Instagram - Snapchat - Facebook - Youtube - Discord - Twitter - BeReal - LinkedIn - TikTok - WeChat - Telegram - Reddit
	GAQ2: When all of my friends use an app that I don't have, this makes me want to use that app despite the concerns I have about that app.	Likert scale (1- 5) - Strongly agree - Strongly disagree
	GAQ3: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my personal data (e.g. location, health, financial, contact, and other personally identifying information)	Likert scale (1 -5) - Extremely concerned - Not at all concerned
	GAQ4: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my user-generated content (e.g. emails, messages, calendar data, contacts, gameplay information, audio, video, and photo content)	Likert scale (1- 5) - Strongly agree - Strongly disagree
	GAQ5: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my protected resources (e.g. Bluetooth peripherals, home automation features, Wi-Fi connections, and local networks)	Open answer

Table 2. Measurement Items for the Intention to use a social media app

Variable	Measurement Item	Type
Length of Privacy Statement	LPS1: How often do you read the terms and conditions of a social media app?	Likert scale (1-5) - Always - Never
	LPS2: I understand the terms and conditions of social media apps clearly	Likert scale (1-5) -Strongly Agree - Strongly Disagree
	LPS3: I am more likely to read a privacy statement when it is easy to read	Likert scale (1-5) -Strongly Agree - Strongly Disagree
	LPS4: How much time are you willing to spend on reading a privacy statement of a social media app?	Slider 0 - 60 minutes
	LPS5: If I have to scroll continuously through a privacy statement it makes me uninterested in an app	Likert scale (1-5) -Strongly Agree - Strongly Disagree
	LPS6: If I have to scroll continuously through a privacy statement it makes me uninstall the app	Likert scale (1-5) -Strongly Agree - Strongly Disagree
	LPS7: In a few words explain what may prevent you from reading privacy statements?	Open-ended question
App Permission Requests:	APR1: In which of the following app permission requests have you granted permission, regarding your settings for social media apps in general?	Multiple choice Personal data User-generated content Protected resources Device capabilities The device's advertising identifier
	APR2: I am still willing to use my favourite social media app even if the app need permission of the following data: · Contacts · Photos · Bluetooth · Microphone · Camera · Files · Location	
	APR3: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my personal data (e.g. location, health, financial, contact, and other personally identifying information)	
	APR4: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my user-generated content (e.g. emails, messages, calendar data, contacts, gameplay information, audio, video, and photo content)	Likert scale (1-5) -Strongly Agree - Strongly Disagree
	APR5: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my protected resources (e.g. Bluetooth peripherals, home automation features, Wi-Fi connections, and local networks)	
	APR6: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my device capabilities (e.g. camera and microphone)	
	APR7: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my device's advertising identifier: which enables app tracking	

RESULTS

As a result a total number of 106 respondents filled in the survey successfully. The respondents consisted of 50 males, and 56 females. The mean of the age of the 106 respondents was 22.96 with a standard deviation of 2.44 and a minimum of 17 and maximum of 33. All respondents are also current university students in the Netherlands.

In spite of their prior privacy concerns, 33.96% of the respondents would use a social media app because they tend to feel social pressure from their surroundings, however 49.05% of the respondents does not feel the social pressure to download a social media app regardless the usages of the social media apps in their network. Generally, the majority (75.48%) of the respondents are concerned about their own privacy on social media apps. While 66.98% of the respondents are concerned that the social media app intrudes on their privacy.

The reliability of the survey measures are determined by using the Cronbach Alpha displayed below in table 2.

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Length of Privacy statement	0.461	5
App Permission Requests	0.753	5

There were seven questions asked for the results of the variable “the length of privacy statement”. To the first question how often a respondent reads the terms and conditions of a social media, of the respondents 57.55% never reads them, 29.25% rarely reads them, 11.32% read it sometimes and 1.89% read them often. While 0 respondents always read the terms and conditions. The results are shown in figure 2.

How often the respondents read the terms and conditions of social media apps

Figure 2. Results on how often a respondent reads the terms and conditions of a social media app.

The results of the statement if a respondent understands the terms and conditions of social

media apps clearly are shown in figure 3. It's clear that 37.74% find that they are neutral on this.

Statement: I understand the terms and conditions of social media apps clearly

Figure 3. Results understanding the terms and conditions of social media apps clearly statement

48.11% of the respondents are more likely to read a privacy statement when it is easy to read. And 21.7% strongly agree with this statement. Against the 16.98% who are neutral on this statement and the 13.21% who either disagree or strongly disagree. These results are also shown in figure 4.

Statement: I am more likely to read a privacy statement when it is easy to read

Figure 4. Results of more likely to read a privacy statement when it is easy to read statement

The average time in minutes respondents are willing to spend on reading a privacy statement of a social media app is 4.46 minutes with a minimum of 0 and a maximum of 30 minutes and a variance of 17.02 minutes

48.11% of the respondents (strongly) agree with the statement that if they have to continuously scroll through a privacy statement, it will make them uninterested in an app. The results are shown in figure 5.

Statement: If I have to scroll continuously through a privacy statement it makes me uninterested in an app

Figure 5. Results to “If I have to scroll continuously through a privacy statement this makes me

uninterested in an app” statement

To the statement “If I have to scroll continuously through a privacy statement, it makes me uninstall an app” 48.12% of the respondents (strongly) disagree with this. The full results are shown in figure 6.

Statement: If I have to scroll continuously through a privacy statement it makes me uninstall the app

Figure 6. Results to “If I have to scroll continuously through a privacy statement this makes me uninstall the app” statement

Lastly, a majority of the respondents find the length of the privacy statement, the use of jargon, their own laziness, that they are not interested in the privacy statement since they have to agree either way if they want to use an app preventing them from reading the privacy statements of the social media apps.

As for the results of the variable: ‘app permission requests’, seven questions were asked. The first question was asked to give an insight into which kind of different app permission requests respondents have granted permission on their social media app, table 2 visualises the answer of respondents. The three most common granted app permissions respondents have are device capabilities (92.45%), user-generated content (91.13%) and personal data (69.81%).

Table 2. Current social media app permission settings

Current social media app permission settings	Percentage	Choice Count
Personal data: including location, health, financial, contact, and other personally identifying information	69.81%	74
User-generated content: like emails, messages, calendar data, contacts, gameplay information, music activity, audio, video, and photo content	81.13%	86
Protected resources: like Bluetooth peripherals, home automation features, Wi-Fi connections, and local networks	48.11%	51
Device capabilities: like camera and microphone	92.45%	98
The device’s advertising identifier: which enables app tracking	53.77%	57

Figures 7 through 11 discusses whether users are willing to use a social media app if it has access to various app permission requests. Starting with personal data the responses were evenly dispersed. One third of respondents, agrees, are neutral and disagrees with granting permission of personal data. Overall the willingness of respondents were willing to grant permission to social media app permissions, as the option “agree” was the most

chosen option regarding access to personal data, user-generated content and protected resources. Furthermore, the access to user-generated content is the only app permission request, where the majority of the respondents voted to “disagree”(31.13%).

Statement: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my personal data

Figure 7. Results to use a social media app if it has access to personal data

Statement: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my user-generated content

Figure 8. Results to use a social media app if it has access to the user-generated content

Statement: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my protected resources

Figure 9. Results to use a social media app if it has access to the protected resources

Statement: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my device capabilities

Figure 10. Results to use a social media app if it has access to the device capabilities

Statement: I am still willing to use a social media app if it has access to my device's advertising identifier (app tracking)

Figure 11. Results to use a social media app if it has access to the device's advertising identifier

As for the app tracking social media apps, it was interesting to note that the distribution between male and females was significantly different. As females were as 40% of the females are more likely not to grant permission to social media apps if it enables app tracking than males (16%).

DISCUSSION

Cronbach's alpha analysis was conducted on the variable "length of privacy statement". It was found that the variable's alpha level was .461, which indicates that the variable does not have an adequate level of inter-item reliability. However, it was found that deleting any of the items would not significantly increase the alpha level. On the other hand, Cronbach's alpha on the variable "app permission requests", had an alpha level of .753, which indicates that the variable has an adequate level of inter-item reliability.

Network effect, the construct used to measure the popularity of an app, influences the interest one has to use social media. The study found that $\frac{1}{3}$ of the respondents are still willing to continue using a social media app, due to the fact of feeling left out, despite having concerns about mobile privacy.

In this paper it is hard to determine the positive influence because of the SPSS analysis that could not be conducted. In relation to the first hypothesis, "the of a privacy statement" (H1). the results show that the length of a privacy statement does not have any effect on the user's intention to use an app. However, it is interesting to mention that the average time that the respondents are willing to spend on reading the privacy statement is 4.46 minutes. It is found that respondents will still have intention to use a social media app despite it being long. This is due to the fact that they are able to scroll through the text and click agree without reading the privacy statement.

On the other hand, regarding the hypothesis of the "amount of app permission requests" (H2), it shows that the amount of app permission requests does not have a significant influence on the user's

intention to use a social media app. The amount of app permission requests still will not hinder the respondents to use a social media app.

CONCLUSION

The study has found that the students in the Netherlands generally do not read the terms and conditions of a social media app, concluding that the length of the privacy statement does not matter, since this will not be read regardless of the length. The students are divided on the acceptance of app permission requests, concluding that the amount of requests does not negatively affect the intention to use the applications. Summarising the results of this study, the privacy statements of social media apps do not affect the attractiveness of using a social media app.

Implications

This study is constrained by the following limitations. First, this study is limited to Dutch university students as only Dutch university students participated in this study, however the researchers think that the survey given in another country would lead to the same results so the results are likely to be generalizable. Secondly, given the short period of time of this study, the target sample size was not realised, as this study is based on a sample size of 106. Third, the study gathered information using an online survey, which is vulnerable to self-selection bias (Kim, Lee, Han & Lee, 2002). Fourth, the Cronbach's alpha analysis on the first variable "length of privacy statement" indicates that the survey has not an adequate level of inter-item reliability. Lastly this study only looked at the popular social media apps, which also limits the results of this study.

Further research

For future research some of the metrics employed in this study may need to be changed in order to get better findings. It is recommended to substitute the five-point likert scale with a seven, nine or ten point likert scale. In order to get a higher Cronbach's alpha and eventually a more reliable measure. There is also a possibility to include different variables as there are many other reasons on why a person uses an application. Lastly, future research could involve less popular social media applications in relation to digital privacy and intention to use a social media app.

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